

Multidimensional Generalized Arithmetic Progressions of Multiplicity One

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 29 April 2026</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav</p>	<p>This article is a review work to expose the extended concepts of arithmetic progressions originating by applying the concepts of an arbitrary dimension and a fixed multiplicity (one but can be expanded for more than one also) applied on different common differences, which was published in chapters seven and eight in two books on multidimensional arithmetic progressions cited in the references and in the article. In this article we will report the advanced arithmetic progressions with multiplicity one of different dimensions from one to r and will discuss the formula to find their general terms and the sums of first n terms. We have left the discussion on the formulae to find the arithmetic means between any two arbitrary members of such generalized progressions so that mathematics teachers and learners can find it for useful teaching with a new look and a research oriented approach. Thus, the article opens many new areas of research and its applications.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: arithmetic progression, generalized arithmetic progression, common difference, dimension, multiplicity, sum of terms.</p> <p>AMS Subject Classification 2020: 40-02, 40B05, 40D99, 97F10</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

In mathematics, the study of patterns leads to many significant mathematical generalizations. The succession of numbers (real or complex) designated as the first term, the second term, the third term and so on gives rise to what we name it a sequence or a progression. Such progression is then divided into arithmetic, geometric, harmonic, etc. (James & James, 2001; Katz, 2019; Progression - Wikipedia contributors, 2025; Sequence - Wikipedia contributors, 2026; Yadav, 2008a, 2008b, 2010, 2020, 2026; Yadav et al., 2026).

A progression is a collection of numbers (may be repeated or different) in a fixed order followed by a specific rule. The terms of the sequence are called elements or terms or members. In a set we don't repeat elements but in a sequence we can repeat it multiple times following a definite order. In progression the order of the terms matter whereas in a set order doesn't matter. It is finite or infinite as per the number of terms. It is denoted by its n th term, where n denotes the n th element of the progression. We can represent the finite progression (sequence) having its n th term as t_n by $(t_n)_{n=1}^r$, where r is a natural number. The infinite sequence for the same n th term of the sequence is denoted by $(t_n)_{n=1}^{\infty}$,

where n is a natural number (James & James, 2001; Progression - Wikipedia contributors, 2025; Sequence - Wikipedia contributors, 2026; Yadav, 2008a, 2008b, 2010, 2020, 2026; Yadav et al., 2026).

The sum of the terms of a progression makes a series denoted by $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} t_n = t_1 + t_2 + t_3 + \dots$, where t_n is the n th term of the sequence. The partial sum of the series is obtained by replacing the infinity symbol with a finite number (say N) as $\sum_{n=1}^N t_n = t_1 + t_2 + t_3 + \dots + t_N$. Generally it is denoted by S_N . If the partial sum converges, we say that the infinite series is convergent (Convergent series - Wikipedia contributors, 2025; Progression - Wikipedia contributors, 2025; Sequence - Wikipedia contributors, 2026; Series (mathematics) - Wikipedia contributors, 2026; Ulas, 2005; Yadav, 2008a, 2008b, 2010, 2020, 2026; Yadav et al., 2026).

As discussed earlier a progression may be divided into many parts out of which the one is the arithmetic progression (Arithmetic progression - Wikipedia contributors, 2026; Dawson, 2012; Progression - Wikipedia contributors, 2025). It is a progression of numbers based on the fact that the difference from any succeeding term to its preceding term remains a fixed constant throughout the entire progression.

The fixed difference is called a common difference of the arithmetic progression. In it we study about the general term, particular term, sum of the first n and infinite terms and some properties. A finite part of an arithmetic progression is called a finite arithmetic progression. The sum of a finite arithmetic progression is called an arithmetic series (Arithmetic progression - Wikipedia contributors, 2026; Convergent series - Wikipedia contributors, 2025; Progression - Wikipedia contributors, 2025; Series (mathematics) - Wikipedia contributors, 2026; Yadav, 2008a, 2008b, 2010, 2020, 2026; Yadav et al., 2026).

2. PRELIMINARIES

3.1. General Term Formulae: Let us discuss the general formulae for nth terms of different arithmetic progressions of multiplicity one with different dimensions one by one and then generalize it for rth dimension arithmetic progression of multiplicity one.

We know that for one dimensional arithmetic progressions of multiplicity one, the standard form of 1-D.A.P.M. (1) is

$$a, (a + d_1), (a + 2d_1), (a + 3d_1), \dots$$

and its general term for nth term is given by

$$T_n = a + (n - 1)d_1$$

For two dimensional arithmetic progressions of multiplicity one, the standard form of 2-D.A.P.M. (1) is

$$a, (a + d_1), (a + d_1 + d_2), (a + 2d_1 + d_2), (a + 2d_1 + 2d_2), (a + 3d_1 + d_2), \dots$$

and its general term for nth term given by Yadav (2008) is

$$\begin{aligned} T_{2m-1} = t_n = t_{2m-1} = t_{1,3,5,\dots} &= a + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2) \\ &= a + \frac{(n - 1)}{2}(d_1 + d_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{2m} = t_n = t_{2m} = t_{2,4,6,\dots} &= (a + d_1) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2) \\ &= (a + d_1) + \frac{(n - 2)}{2}(d_1 + d_2) \end{aligned}$$

For three dimensional arithmetic progressions of multiplicity one, the standard form of 3-D.A.P.M. (1) is

$a, a + d_1, a + d_1 + d_2, a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3, a + 2d_1 + d_2 + d_3, a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + d_3, a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3, a + 3d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3$, and so on, whose general term for n term given by Yadav (2010) are

$$\begin{aligned} T_{3m-2} = t_n = t_{3m-2} = t_{1,4,7,\dots} &= a + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3) \\ &= a + \frac{(n - 1)}{3}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{3m-1} = t_n = t_{3m-1} = t_{2,5,8,\dots} &= (a + d_1) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3) \\ &= (a + d_1) + \frac{(n - 2)}{3}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{3m} = t_n = t_{3m} = t_{3,6,9,\dots} &= (a + d_1 + d_2) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3) \\ &= (a + d_1 + d_2) + \frac{(n - 3)}{3}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly for four dimensional arithmetic progressions of multiplicity one, we may write the standard form of 4-D.A.P.M. (1) as

$a, a + d_1, a + d_1 + d_2, a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3, a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4, a + 2d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4, a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + d_3 + d_4, a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3 + d_4, a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3 + 2d_4, a + 3d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3 + 2d_4, a + 3d_1 + 3d_2 + 2d_3 + 2d_4$, and so on.

Whose general terms for nth term will be given by

$$\begin{aligned} T_{4m-3} = t_n = t_{4m-3} = t_{1,5,9,\dots} &= a + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4) \\ &= a + \frac{(n - 1)}{4}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{4m-2} = t_n = t_{4m-2} = t_{2,6,10,\dots} &= (a + d_1) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4) \\ &= (a + d_1) + \frac{(n - 2)}{4}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4) \end{aligned}$$

To understand the article we should have the basic knowledge of multiplicity, dimension, multiple arithmetic progressions, K-dimensional generalized arithmetic progressions, and K-dimensional generalized arithmetic progressions with multiplicity m discussed by Yadav (2008a, 2008b, 2010, 2020, 2026), Yadav et al. (2026) and in the references.

3. DISCUSSION

Following the notations and basic mathematical terms for the progressions discussed by Yadav (2008a, 2008b, 2010, 2020, 2026), we denote multi-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity one by M.D.A.P.M. (1). Now we start the discussion from finding the general terms.

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$$T_{4m-1} = t_n = t_{4m-1} = t_{3,7,11,\dots} = (a + d_1 + d_2) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4)$$

$$= (a + d_1 + d_2) + \frac{(n - 3)}{4}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4)$$

$$T_{4m} = t_n = t_{4m} = t_{4,8,12,\dots} = (a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4)$$

$$= (a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3) + \frac{(n - 4)}{4}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4)$$

Proceeding in the way discussed above, we can generalize the formulae for general terms for nth terms for rth dimensional arithmetic progressions of multiplicity one. For rth dimensional arithmetic progressions of multiplicity one, the standard form of r-D.A.P.M. (1) would be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & a \\
 & a + d_1 \\
 & a + d_1 + d_2 \\
 & a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 \\
 & a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 \\
 & \dots \\
 & a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r \\
 & a + 2d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r \\
 & a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r \\
 & \dots \\
 & a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3 + \dots + 2d_r \\
 & a + 3d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3 + \dots + 2d_r \\
 & \dots \\
 & a + 3d_1 + 3d_2 + 3d_3 + \dots + 3d_r \\
 & \dots \\
 & a + 3m + md_2 + md_3 + \dots + md_r \\
 & \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

Following the steps discussed above its general term for nth term will be given by r different formulae as follows:

$$T_{rm-(r-1)} = t_n = t_{rm-(r-1)} = t_{1,(r+1),(2r+1),\dots}$$

$$= a + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)$$

$$= a + \frac{(n - 1)}{r}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)$$

$$T_{rm-(r-2)} = t_n = t_{rm-(r-2)} = t_{2,(r+2),(2r+2),\dots}$$

$$= (a + d_1) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)$$

$$= (a + d_1) + \frac{(n - 2)}{r}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)$$

$$T_{rm-(r-3)} = t_n = t_{rm-(r-3)} = t_{3,(r+3),(2r+3),\dots}$$

$$= (a + d_1 + d_2) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)$$

$$= (a + d_1 + d_2) + \frac{(n - 3)}{r}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)$$

Similarly the last one is

$$T_{rm-(r-r)} = t_n = t_{rm-(r-r)} = t_{r,2r,3r,\dots}$$

$$= (a + d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_{r-1}) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)$$

$$= (a + d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_{r-1}) + \frac{(n - r)}{r}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)$$

3.2. Rule to Write the General Formula for General Term: First we write the general term of the subscripts of different terms as

$$T_{rm-(r-\alpha)} = t_n = t_{rm-(r-\alpha)} = t_{r,2r,3r,\dots}$$

Then the general term would be written as

$$(a + d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_{\alpha-1}) + \frac{(n - \alpha)}{r}(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)$$

where $(a + d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_{\alpha-1})$ is the sum of first α terms of the given progression. That is, the general formula of all the above formulae is

$$T_{rm-(r-\alpha)} = t_n = t_{rm-(r-\alpha)}$$

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$$= (a + d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_{\alpha-1}) + \frac{(n - \alpha)}{r} (d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)$$

3.3. Sum Formula: We know that for one dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity one, we get the arithmetic series

$$a + (a + d_1) + (a + 2d_1) + (a + 3d_1) + \dots$$

and its sum is given by

$$S_n = \frac{n}{2} [2a + (n - 1)d_1]$$

We also know that for two dimensional arithmetic progressions with multiplicity one, we get the following series

$$a + (a + d_1) + (a + d_1 + d_2) + (a + 2d_1 + d_2) + (a + 2d_1 + 2d_2) + (a + 3d_1 + d_2) + \dots$$

and its sum is given by two formulae of different terms (Yadav, 2008)

$$S_{2m-1} = \frac{m}{2} [2a + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2)]; \text{ where } n = 2m - 1$$

$$S_{2m} = \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2)]; \text{ where } n = 2m$$

For every n, we can find m for each of the above two formulae, then adding them we find the sum of the series as

$$S_n = S_{2m-1} + S_{2m}$$

For three dimensional arithmetic progressions with multiplicity one, we get the series

$$a + (a + d_1) + (a + d_1 + d_2) + (a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3) + (a + 2d_1 + d_2 + d_3) + \\ (a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + d_3) + (a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3) + (a + 3d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3) + \dots$$

and its sum is given by three formulae of different terms (Yadav, 2010)

$$S_{3m-2} = \frac{m}{2} [2a + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3)]; \text{ where } n = 3m - 2$$

$$S_{3m-1} = \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3)]; \text{ where } n = 3m - 1$$

$$S_{3m} = \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1 + d_2) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3)]; \text{ where } n = 3m$$

For every n, we can find m for each of the above three formulae, then adding them we find the sum of the series as

$$S_n = S_{3m-2} + S_{3m-1} + S_{3m}$$

Similarly for four dimensional arithmetic progressions with multiplicity one, we will get the series

$$a + (a + d_1) + (a + d_1 + d_2) + (a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3) + (a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4) + \\ (a + 2d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4) + (a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + d_3 + d_4) + (a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3 + d_4) + \\ (a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3 + 2d_4) + \dots$$

and its sum will be given by four formulae of different terms

$$S_{4m-3} = \frac{m}{2} [2a + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4)]; \text{ where } n = 4m - 3$$

$$S_{4m-2} = \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4)]; \text{ where } n = 4m - 2$$

$$S_{4m-1} = \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1 + d_2) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4)]; \text{ where } n = 4m - 1$$

$$S_{4m} = \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4)]; \text{ where } n = 4m$$

For every n, we can find m for each of the above four formulae, then adding them we find the sum of the series as

$$S_n = S_{4m-3} + S_{4m-2} + S_{4m-1} + S_{4m}$$

Proceeding in the way discussed above, we can generalize the formulae for sum of the first n terms for rth dimensional arithmetic progressions of multiplicity one. For it we get the series

$$a + (a + d_1) + (a + d_1 + d_2) + (a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3) + (a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4) + \dots + \\ (a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r) + (a + 2d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r) + (a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r) + \\ \dots + (a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3 + \dots + 2d_r) + (a + 3d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3 + \dots + 2d_r) + \dots + \\ (a + 3d_1 + 3d_2 + 3d_3 + \dots + 3d_r) + \dots + (a + 3m + md_2 + md_3 + \dots + md_r) + \dots$$

Following the steps discussed above its sum for first n terms will be given by r different formulae as follows:

$$S_{mr-(r-1)} = \frac{m}{2} [2a + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)]; \text{ where } n = mr - (r - 1)$$

$$S_{mr-(r-2)} = \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)]; \text{ where } n = mr - (r - 2)$$

$$S_{mr-(r-3)} = \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1 + d_2) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)]; \text{ where } n = mr - (r - 3)$$

...

$$S_{mr-1} = \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_{r-2}) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)]; \text{ where } n = mr - 1$$

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$$S_{mr} = \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_{r-1}) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + \dots + d_r)]; n = mr$$

For every n, we can find m for each of the above r formulae. Then adding them we can find

$$S_n = S_{mr-(r-1)} + S_{mr-(r-2)} + \dots + S_{mr-1} + S_{rm}.$$

Example 3.1: Write 6-D.A.P.M. (1) for first term 2 and common differences 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8.

Here we have $a = 2, d_1 = 3, d_2 = 4, d_3 = 5, d_4 = 6, d_5 = 7, d_6 = 8$, then the 6-D.A.P.M. (1) will be as follows

$$\begin{aligned} a &= 2 \\ a + d_1 &= 5 \\ a + d_1 + d_2 &= 9 \\ a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 &= 14 \\ a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 &= 20 \\ a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 &= 27 \\ a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6 &= 35 \\ a + 2d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6 &= 38 \\ a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6 &= 42 \\ a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6 &= 47 \\ a + 2d_1 + 2d_2 + 2d_3 + 2d_4 + d_5 + d_6 &= 53 \end{aligned}$$

60, 68, 71, 75, 80, 86, 93, 101, 104, 108, 113, 119, 126, 134, 137, 141, ...

Example 3.2: Find 21th to 27th terms of the 6-D.A.P.M. (1), where

$a = 2, d_1 = 3, d_2 = 4, d_3 = 5, d_4 = 6, d_5 = 7, d_6 = 8$.

Here we have $r = 6$, then

$$\begin{aligned} t_{21} &= t_{6m-3(m=4)} = t_{6m-(6-3)} \\ &= (a + d_1 + d_2) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6) \\ &= (2 + 3 + 4) + (4 - 1)(3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8) = 9 + 99 = 108 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{22} &= t_{6m-2(m=4)} = t_{6m-(6-4)} \\ &= (a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6) \\ &= (2 + 3 + 4 + 5) + (4 - 1)(3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8) = 14 + 99 = 113 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{23} &= t_{6m-1(m=4)} = t_{6m-(6-5)} \\ &= (a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6) \\ &= (2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6) + (4 - 1)(3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8) = 20 + 99 = 119 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{24} &= t_{6m(m=4)} = t_{6m-(6-6)} \\ &= (a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6) \\ &= (2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7) + (4 - 1)(3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8) = 27 + 99 = 126 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{25} &= t_{6m-5(m=5)} = t_{6m-(6-1)} \\ &= a + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6) \\ &= 2 + (5 - 1)(3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8) = 2 + 132 = 134 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{26} &= t_{6m-4(m=5)} = t_{6m-(6-2)} \\ &= (a + d_1) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6) \\ &= (2 + 3) + (5 - 1)(3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8) = 5 + 132 = 137 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t_{27} &= t_{6m-3(m=5)} = t_{6m-(6-3)} \\ &= (a + d_1 + d_2) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6) \\ &= (2 + 3 + 4) + (5 - 1)(3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8) = 9 + 132 = 141 \end{aligned}$$

Exercise 3.3: Find the sum of the first 27 terms of a 6DAPM (1) where

$$a = 2, d_1 = 3, d_2 = 4, d_3 = 5, d_4 = 6, d_5 = 7, d_6 = 8.$$

Here $r = 6$ and $n = 27 = 6.m - 3; m = 5$. Therefore each of $S_{6m-5}, S_{6m-4}, S_{6m-3}$ have 5 and each of $S_{6m-2}, S_{6m-1}, S_{6m}$ have 4 have terms like

$$\begin{aligned} S_{6m-5} &= S_{6.5-5 (r=6, m=5)} = S_{6.5-(6-1)} \\ &= \frac{m}{2} [2a + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6)] = \frac{5}{2} [4 + 4.33] = 340 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} S_{6m-4} &= S_{6.5-4 (r=6, m=5)} = S_{6.5-(6-2)} \\ &= \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6)] = \frac{5}{2} [10 + 4.33] = 355 \end{aligned}$$

$$S_{6m-3} = S_{6.5-3 (r=6, m=5)} = S_{6.5-(6-3)}$$

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$$= \frac{m}{2} [2(a + d_1 + d_2) + (m - 1)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6)] = \frac{5}{2} [18 + 4.33] = 375$$

$$\begin{aligned} S_{6m-2} &= S_{6.5-2} (r=6, m=5) = S_{6.5-(6-4)} \\ &= \frac{(m-1)}{2} [2(a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3) + (m-2)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6)] \\ &= \frac{4}{2} [28 + 99] = 254 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} S_{6m-1} &= S_{6.5-1} (r=6, m=5) = S_{6.5-(6-5)} \\ &= \frac{(m-1)}{2} [2(a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4) + (m-2)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6)] \\ &= \frac{4}{2} [40 + 99] = 278 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} S_{6m} &= S_{6.5-0} (r=6, m=5) = S_{6.5-(6-6)} \\ &= \frac{(m-1)}{2} [2(a + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5) + (m-2)(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 + d_4 + d_5 + d_6)] \\ &= \frac{4}{2} [54 + 99] = 306 \end{aligned}$$

Adding all we get

$$\begin{aligned} S_{27} &= S_{6m-5} + S_{6m-4} + S_{6m-3} + S_{6m-2} + S_{6m-1} + S_{6m} \\ &= 340 + 355 + 375 + 254 + 278 + 306 = 1908. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly multidimensional arithmetic progressions of different multiplicities i.e. r-dimensional arithmetic progressions with multiplicity m, where $r = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$ and $m = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$ can be further extended for the cases as: 1-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity 2, 1-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity 3, ..., 1-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity m; 2-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity 3, 2-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity 4, ..., 2-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity m; 3-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity 4, 3-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity 5, ..., 3-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity m; r-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity 2, r-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity 3, ..., r-dimensional arithmetic progression with multiplicity m; ... Although 1-D.A.P. (m) is nothing but 1-D.A.P. (1). The concept of multiplicity does not change the nature of the arithmetic progressions of one dimension. The nature of many properties of 1-D.A.P. (1) has not been developed parallel for other types of arithmetic progressions. They can be propounded for them as the extension and research work.

4. CONCLUSION

Only two properties of arithmetic progressions of dimension one and multiplicity one have been extended for higher dimension and multiplicities, the general terms and the sum of the n terms. This is a big limitation of this article that we cannot write the general terms, sum of the series in a single formula. We have also not discussed the arithmetic means between two terms for higher dimension and multiplicity, although we can write them for different cases depending on the dimension and multiplicity.

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